

NATIONAL IDEA AS A CONSOLIDATING PRINCIPLE OF UNIVERSITY EDUCATION

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ABSTRACT

The object of research is national education of students in the university environment.

Investigated problem. As a result of a critical analysis of the works of Ukrainian scholars, the issue under investigation has been solved. The status of contemporary higher education in Ukraine, and the processes that can negatively affect it have been analyzed. The state holistic strategy of national education for young people, enshrined in the legislative documents of various ministries and departments has been investigated. The views of western scholars on the discussed problem have been regarded, as a result, the implementation of a new term has been identified.

Main scientific results. The fundamental goals and basic tasks of a national idea implementation in the general system of Ukrainian education have been determined. The complex perspectives of an up-to-date teachers' training which can be regarded controversial in terms of new challenges in Ukrainian society have been outlined. Much attention has been paid to the issues national identity, national values and patriotism of students through the prism of global values and tolerant relationship. The idea of close cooperation necessity between ministries and educational institutions aimed at establishing peaceful and friendly relations between residents of different regions of Ukraine has been expressed. The idea of national consolidation on the basis of common cultural and historical past, national values and interests has been defined as the principal factor in the university students' education.

Scope of practical application. The results of the research can be used in both cognitive and educational values.

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1. Introduction

1. 1. The object of research

National education of students in the university environment.

1. 2. Problem description

Reflecting on Ukrainian educational processes, which are constantly undergoing transformations both in form and in content – from urgent and successful to instant and lightning-fast, affected by political crises and, more recently, by the pandemic – we have come to the conclusion that in order to navigate the learning environment, it is necessary to identify the dominant feature of the educational process. The global problems of humanity such as the environmental crisis, military conflicts, pandemic and man-made disasters remain unresolved. Scholars and researches now speak of a profound crisis of civilization, on the threats facing humanity. Education therefore has the important mission of finding decisive and effective solutions to overcome the crisis and, in our opinion this requires the priority development of culture, education and upbringing.

New times bring unprecedented demands on society, new challenges for education, different needs and current problems that affect today's tasks and innovative ways of solving them. Certainly, the given context and individual dependencies on negative influences and processes that are taking place, considering the current teachers' training system, the emergence of a new generation of teachers with a high level of profound pedagogical culture is essential.

Let's believe that the goal of society should necessarily coincide with the strategic goals of education. "The idea of the new Ukrainian school requires important aspects of education of the

future, and therefore of Ukraine of the future, education based on human values. The competence approach in education is not a single method of training a modern practitioner, by interfering only with this goal, we risk to raise one day a generation of professional manipulators and cheaters, that can lead the people down a maddening path to the abyss" [1].

In the process of theoretical analysis it is possible to come to the conclusion that further productive scientific and pedagogical understanding of the problem of students' national education is impossible without profound analysis of this area as the subject of study and as components of the educational process in the university environment.

1. 3. Suggested solution to the problem

The development of cultural and spiritual characteristics of the individual is best based on the national idea, i.e. a system of views, beliefs, ideals, and traditions, which allows forming world-views and values of young people in the priority direction of civilization.

Scholars and practitioners, teachers and educators are looking for concrete content, forms, methods and technologies that can become a powerful mechanism in the process of creating of educational conditions in the university environment for the formation of true citizens and patriots of their country. This educational situation is a serious challenge to pedagogical science, as this educational field still lacks scientifically sound projects and valid psychological, pedagogical and methodological recommendations.

The aim of research is to accent the idea of the national education in the university as an objective priority, since it is aimed at ensuring the integrity of Ukraine, which is the core of the Ukrainian national idea.

2. Materials and Methods

A set of research methods was used to solve the issues under investigation, in particular: analysis and synthesis of scientific developments, legislative and normative-legal documents, historical and pedagogical sources, generalizations for summarizing and formulating conclusions; bibliographic method for obtaining information for creating the main array of sources and their further systematization. The combination of these methods provided an objective assessment, selection and analysis of the source base, determination of theoretical principles, reliability of the obtained results and generalization of research findings.

3. Results

It should be noted that a number of documents approved by the Ministry of Education and Science of Ukraine, the Ministry of Youth and Sports of Ukraine and the Cabinet of Ministers has become an immediate basis for the implementation of the important needs for the preservation of the Ukrainian nation, since education is the basis on which the crucial characteristics of a cultural person and a citizen are cemented, i.e. a person's national identity, national ideology, patriotism, tolerance, empathy and personal culture. It concerns the state holistic strategy of national education for young people, enshrined in the legislative documents of various ministries and departments. The documents are principal since they deal with "Conception of National-Patriotic Education in the Educational System of Ukraine" [2], "The Approved Plan of Activities for National and Patriotic Education of Youth for 2021" [2]; competitions to identify national-patriotic education projects, for the implementation of which financial support is provided; All-Ukrainian Training "Guards of Ukrainian State"; All-Ukrainian Action "Let Us Respect"; All-Ukrainian Conference "Language as the Basic Identifier of the People", etc.

Ukrainian regions, which were formed at different historical times and by different states, have significant differences between each other for their historical structure. This not only affects the worldview of people, but under the conditions of geopolitical non-recognition of the Ukrainian state tends to aggravate [3]. In this regard, the establishment of the Expert Committee of the Ministry of Culture on Ethnic Policy at the beginning of 2017 was a matter of urgency. It is aimed at analyzing public processes and making suggestions that can help avoid interethnic conflicts and build mutual understanding between ethnic communities in Ukraine. The opening of new institutions in form and significant in content is an adequate challenge to modern Ukrainian realities.

In today's ambiguous situation and worldview confrontations among Ukrainians, close, long-term and systematic cooperation of this Council with Ukrainian universities seems extremely useful and relevant, as their strategic goals coincide.

According to UN and UNESCO documents, a nation state is a state in which the titular people constitute 67 % of the country's population. According to the 2001 All-Ukrainian Population Census, there are 37,541,693 Ukrainians by nationality, representing 77.82 % of the total population [4].

Such high statistical data, the social situation in our country, transformations in the social, political and economic life, reevaluation of values in the minds of people enable us to identify the national-patriotic education in the university as an objective priority, because it is "driven by the process of formation of a single political nation in Ukraine, aimed at ensuring the integrity, unity of Ukraine, which is the core of the Ukrainian national idea" [5].

Global and domestic processes to some extent affect education. The pedagogical realities of today require the solution of contradictory problems. Leading European countries have largely abandoned the trendy multicultural education in the twentieth century and now pursue a policy of adaptation of minorities and migrants to the people in whose territory they live.

At the same time, having set its development vector on the European and global dimension, our state demands that Ukrainian education create conditions for the embracing of other peoples' cultures, shaping young people's tolerant attitude and empathy for European and world values, while emphasizing the need to preserve traditions of national culture, fostering a sense of national identity and national dignity. This means that university education should become a platform for understanding and accepting cultural values, norms, patterns and forms of activities that exist in Ukrainian society.

The dialectics of the interaction of national and universal categories forms the basis of national psychology. National culture is revealed primarily through the spiritual characteristics of the people. Spiritual characteristics are associated with national culture, traditions that are reflected in the minds of people. It is a measure of cultural values.

Every ethnic group has its own original consciousness, mentality, which depends not only on the common language, territory, economic life, but also on the common psychological composition. The religious, moral and aesthetic values of each nation reveal people's commitment for higher ideals, have much in common and are inherited by the next generation. Deep penetration into the sources nourishes and strengthens the culture. The interaction of national cultures enriches them, but isolation from other national cultures threatens savagery.

Ukraine has always had a strong sense of international tolerance and it is one of the most democratic countries in the world when it comes to ethnic groups. This means that the dialogical nature of the culture of communication and coexistence in modern society, even in a changing, politically unstable, visually diverse is primarily important. In this context, the dialogical concept becomes a productive opportunity for education through the deep unity of language and culture, which are the main guides to the identification of the individual as a citizen.

The language is a part of the nation, a means of recognizing its culture and mentality. "The language and the nation are an integral and organic whole. These two concepts completely embedded in each other, one defines the other, each cannot exist without the other. Language is not just a social category which unites people on the basis of understanding, but a national category, because only national language, as an integral part of the national spirit, can serve as a means of holistic understanding and the development of all the creative forces of the nation" [6]. In this regard, the historic event is considered to be the enactment of the Law of Ukraine "On Ensuring the Functioning of the Ukrainian Language as the State Language" on 16 June 2019 [7]. On 16 April 2021 the next step in this direction was made, which led to a new era, as it helped strengthen its status and clarify its important role as the state language in public space, as language is the subject of state language policy in cultural, educational and scientific spheres [8].

The views of the founders of philosophical thought in Ukraine in regard to universal and national values' understanding, and their interconnection and interdependence seem to be relevant in the context of interpreting the contemporary educational realities in Ukraine, since they regarded national values development as only possible on the basis of nationalism, but in the atmosphere of global humanistic ideas" [9].

The fact that every nation is great is of no doubt, through its national mentality and national advantages each nation originally expresses the global universal standards and values to the fullest extent. The purpose of genuine education is to contribute to the formation of such a personality, whose life-giving principle is love for a human being, which is understood in its historical significance. In our opinion, humanity without nationality is just a logical abstraction, but lacking national dignity and homeland identification and involvement a person transmutes into a global orphan.

The implementation of national values and traditions, the elements of folk culture, and the ways of national original communication into the basis of education is a tradition of the Ukrainian scientific community. There is an infinite list of famous Ukrainian educators who contributed much in this sphere, thus their pedagogical heritage is the basis for the modern national idea in the system of Ukrainian higher education.

Cultural identity is an invaluable asset that expands opportunities for a human's inclusive development. But it is renewed and enriched as a result of contact with the traditions and values of other peoples.

It is hardly possible today to find a country with a monoethnic population, and therefore the isolated existence of peoples and cultures in modern world is impossible. Each nation should take into account the factors of its rich interdependence not only with the peoples of the immediate neighborhood, but also with those who are at a distance, but at the same time have an impact on it through economics and politics, through culture and education. The more values a person possesses, the more his/her perception of other cultures, which are distant in time and space, becomes compromised.

In the course of our research we have recorded evidence, though isolated, of different and not always adequate interpretations of such fundamental concepts as "national moral values" and "universal moral values in historical diachronic data. In radical periods of Soviet times, these concepts were artificially delimited; national moral values were humiliated, silenced and often banned.

Our position coincides with the modern vision of national and universal standards' inseparable connection in the educational process, as today's European requirements are the organic integration of national and ethnic values, their essence understanding, their role and interdependence with common human values and interests. "Ukrainian ethnic culture, together with the cultures of other ethnic groups, allows reassessing the world culture, taking the Ukrainian society and Ukrainian personality out of the orbit of the inferiority complex". Nation's intellect, and its ideas and feelings stimulate national optimism of citizens, when everyone, irrespective of their ethnicity, identifies himself/herself as a member of the great national "I AM" [10].

Let's consider the statements of culturologists on the formation of an intelligent personality through the essence of culture to be fundamental, since its core value is transmitted by education; its unity of spiritual and material aspects is the basis of the dialogue of cultures. In such educational context a person acquires humanistic thinking, besides can be realized as an active participant in multicultural space.

Let's interpret the concept "culture" in the context of a pedagogical aspect, and consider teachers as facilitators of social identification, as spiritual mentors of the young, since it is the teacher who provides reproduction of social structures in the process of cultural interaction with students. In this regard two main aspects can be distinguished in the formation of a teacher's personality, i.e. professional and cultural. Professional culture is the content of teachers' training and is modeled according to the objectives of a future teacher and determines his/her professional activity.

Teacher's professional culture is the main goal, the indicator of higher education efficiency and quality. It is an organic combination of pedagogical, psychological, spiritual, methodological, physical culture, and therefore, it is a sign of a harmonious and well-educated personality. "The development of a personality is the basis of its inner harmony, it is manifested in the development of physical and spiritual strength, in the inner unity of theoretical knowledge and practical skills, moral conscience and behavior, in the positive perceptions of society distinctions, in thoughts and feelings balance, in words and actions similarity, and what is principal is how a person identifies himself/herself in his/her beliefs and actions, and what kind of reality he/she belong to as the personality" [11].

The university has to respond to such challenges and adapt to the necessary conditions of raising a new personality with a set of qualities corresponding basically to future leaders. It is the university that has to perform the function of knowledge transferring, the forming of such a mentioned above personality for its further self-realization in social environment. It is for this reason that it is impossible to consider any processes of social development without reference to interaction with higher education institutions. The main task of national education of the Ukrainian university is to provide and meet the public demand for top professionals who are easily navigate in global system of standards and values, perceiving them through national principles, and based on the ideas of national and universal values.

4. Discussion

As a result of the research the basic principles of national education have been revealed. That allowed to focus on its specific characteristics and the content of national education in the university environment.

In the course of our study, the implementation of a new term into global pedagogical science within the problem under study, namely “glonacal development” has been identified, which provides global, national, and local potential support from the higher education system [12]. This confirms the importance of the problem and its wide coverage in scientific circles.

Accelerating globalization processes place a premium on intercultural competencies, both individual and collective, which enable us to manage cultural diversity more effectively and monitor cultural change. Without such competencies, misunderstandings rooted in identity issues are liable to proliferate [13].

In the educational process, language and culture have a common focus on the formation of a humanistic thinking, the perception and realization of the essence of a human being, when he/she realizes his/her place in the system of national coordinates. People are not born social but become such in the process of activity. Education is the process of acquiring individual, personal, national and universal culture, for its further transmission to the next generation. An inclusive national identity can serve as a means for the development of belonging and integration [14].

National identity arises when a nation is perceived as an essential object of human experience. Such experience can be gained in different circumstances, through the prism of war or democracy. Thus, national identities can be very different. Identity can be determined by belonging to an ethnic group or territory, so individuals can simultaneously identify themselves as in the personal ethnic dimension, or global-social, they, in turn, may coincide or differ depending on the situation. It continues to be difficult to grasp, especially with regard to its role in the triangle between state, national community and the individual [15].

Contrary to arguments that the concepts of national identity and state sovereignty have become outmoded, such an inclusive sense of national identity remains critical to maintaining a successful modern political order. National identity not only enhances physical security, but also inspires good governance; facilitates economic development; fosters trust among citizens; engenders support for strong social safety nets; and ultimately makes possible liberal democracy itself [16, 17].

Theory and practice have shown that the universal values of world culture are better understood thanks to their close integration with national culture. For every great nation, foreign patterns are but a source, a stimulus, a breeding ground for its own original creativity. The integration of national and world culture, having regard to world traditions deepens and enriches national culture. The latter, by evolving itself, contributes to the flourishing of national culture. Each national culture and cultural community, with its distinctive identity, has a great universal humanist core, which is reinforced by the convergence and enrichment of different cultures.

Study limitations. The main restrictions on the use of the results, obtained in the study concern:

- 1) age categories of higher education applicants, which are 1st-4th-year university students;
- 2) citizens of Ukraine exceptionally.

The plans for further researches. To solve the problems of national self-identification and verification of the obtained theoretical conclusions, the authors intend to process in their research among 1st–4th-year students of the university by means of psychological and pedagogical methods, such as “Who am I” (M. Coon, T. Portland), “Thinkvein”, and “Press” strategy.

5. Conclusions

Thus, it has been considered that the idea of national consolidation has to be the fundamental task in organizing the educational process in Ukrainian universities. Provided the important components that comprise:

- a) common cultural and historical past;
- b) shared national standards, interests and values;
- c) rejecting the idea of national separateness;
- d) national superiority non-accepting;
- e) different worldview mentality perceiving, education in Ukraine can be safe, fixed, and competitive and satisfy the challenges of Ukrainian educational space.

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